

INFLUENCE OF GRIPPING CONDITION AND MATRIX TYPE ON TENSILE PROPERTIES OF UNIDIRECTIONAL CARBON FIBER REINFORCED THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES

Tsuyoshi MATSUO¹, Masaki HOJO² and Kazuro KAGEYAMA³

¹ School of Engineering, The University of Tokyo

7-3-1 Hongo, Bunkyo-ku, Tokyo, Japan, matsuo@sys.t.u-tokyo.ac.jp

² Department of Mechanical Engineering and Science, Kyoto University, Kyoto
Nishikyo-ku, Kyoto 615-8540, Japan, hojo_cm@me.kyoto-u.ac.jp

³ School of Engineering, The University of Tokyo

7-3-1 Hongo, Bunkyo-ku, Tokyo, Japan, kageyama@giso.t.u-tokyo.ac.jp

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ABSTRACT

Round-robin tests (RRT) have been carried out for the validity of the tensile testing method of unidirectional carbon fiber (CF) reinforced thermoplastic composites (thermoplastic CFRPs). The RRT specially focused on the reproducibility of values obtained by different testing condition by different facility and the effect of the gripping conditions.

For comparison, two kinds of widespread and cost-effective thermoplastic resins were used in this study: polyamide 6 (PA6) and polypropylene (PP). 0° (in fiber direction) tensile properties and 90° (in transverse direction) tensile properties were investigated for both material types base on the international standard test method, ISO 527-5. In both of 0° and 90° test cases, the effects of tabs were verified by comparing the test results with and without tabs.

Detailed investigation on the gripping condition was carried out without tabs in the case of 0° tests for CF/PA6. The tab-less specimens were gripped directly contacting on several types of gripping faces and the influence of the shape of gripping faces were examined together with the insert of the abrasive paper between specimen and grips. As a result, the measured 0° tensile strength with tabs was significantly higher than that without tabs. The specimen with tabs showed tensile fracture at its gauge section, and gave representative evaluation for 0° tensile strength. On the other hand, the specimens gripped directly by rather rough-grip faces without any abrasive paper caused lower-strength results owing to the damage caused by the rough grip faces. From the series of comparison tests, it was clarified that the application of fine-toothed grip faces gave desired test results where its tensile strength is similar to that with tabs and the tensile fracture occurred at the gage section. Thus, the possibility of tab-less tests was indicated as a revision of ISO standard test method.

1 INTRODUCTION

As a leading country for the production of carbon fiber (CF), Japan is responsible for the standardization of the testing method for CF and its composite materials. In past times, Japanese activities for the standardization of tensile test method for unidirectional composites were transferred to international standardization in ISO [1, 2]. Lots of these activities were established as “ISO 527-5:Plastics – Determination of tensile properties/ Part 5 – Testing conditions for unidirectional fibre reinforced composites” [3]. However, these test methods were investigated for thermosetting composites. It has been necessary for them to be applied to thermoplastic composites.

Thermoplastic CFRPs expects to be widely used for various engineering products including automobiles and airplanes owing to their high mechanical properties, lightweight, recyclability and low-cost production [4]. In particular, polypropylene (PP)/CF and polyamide (PA)/CF are suitable for a large scale of production.

In 2014, “the Subcommittee of Standardization of Basic Properties of Thermoplastic CFRP in Japan” was founded in The Japan Plastics Industry Federation by financial support of Ministry of

Economy, Trade and Industry in Japan. The subcommittee started studying tensile, compressive and flexural test methods for thermoplastic CFRP. At first, round-robin tests (RRT) were carried out in order to verify that the conventional tensile test methods could be applied to the tensile properties of unidirectional CF/PP and CF/PA6 in fiber (0°) and transverse (90°) direction. From the RRT results, we pointed out some difficulties in the conventional methods and proposed some methods without tabs. These results and proposals will be reported in ISO/TC61/SC13/WG2 at the 66th ISO Seoul Meeting (17-22 September 2017). This paper presents the procedures and results of these RRTs, and the scientific background.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Materials

This study used two types of laminates manufactured through compression molding by hot-press machine after stacked with several plies of continuous prepregs in a single direction. One of laminates was made from Tencate Cetex TC910 Polyamide 6(PA6)/Carbon fiber unidirectional prepregs and the other was made from Tencate Cetex TC960 Polypropylene(PP)/Carbon fiber unidirectional prepregs. Specifications of both prepreg materials are indicated in Table 1. The volume fractions of TC910 and TC960 are about 43% and 23%, respectively. Then, the effect of matrix type was compared between these two laminates.

Composite product	Tencate Cetex TC910	Tencate Cetex TC960
Fiber	Carbon	Carbon
Matrix	PA 6	PP
Volume fraction of fiber, V_f	43%	23%
Density	1.45 g/cm ³	1.1 g/cm ³
Width	166 mm	165 mm
Thickness	0.16 mm	0.28 mm
Process temperature	249 – 271°C	199 – 216°C

Table 1: Specifications of prepreg tapes [5].

2.2 Round-robin Program

Tab bonding is estimated to be difficult for thermoplastic composites. It is possible to cause interfacial debonding of tabs under tensile loading especially in case of PP-based composites. This study focused on the effects of tab-less grip condition on both 0° and 90° tensile test results.

Round-robin tests were carried out by testing laboratories of twelve members who were from three suppliers of carbon fibers and prepregs, two composite manufacturers, one national agency, one testing machine manufacturer and five Japanese universities. There were eight testing conditions for two materials, two specimens, and whether tab bonding or tab-less as shown in Table 2. Every test was assigned to five laboratories. For the case of 0° tests, 14 specimens were cut from one panel. For 90° tests, 10 specimens were cut from one panel. Specimens were randomly distributed to each laboratory.

Material	CF/PA6				CF/PP			
	0° test		90° test		0° test		90° test	
Specimen	2 mm/min		1 mm/min		2 mm/min		1 mm/min	
Crosshead speed	with tab	tab-less	with tab	tab-less	with tab	tab-less	with tab	tab-less
No. of laboratories	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
No. of specimens	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5

Table 2 : Testing conditions of RRT.

2.3 Specimen

In order to examine these tab-less effects on the strength and elastic modulus of thermoplastic CFRP, RRT specimens were decided as follows referring to the standard test method [3].

2.3.1 Specimen in the fiber direction (0° test)

Specimens with tabs and without tabs were compared in both materials. The tab material for CF/PA6 was ±45 glass woven cloth/PA6, and that for CF/PP was ±45 glass fiber/PP cross ply laminates. All of the tab's thicknesses were 1 mm. Araldite adhesive system was used as tab adhesive. The width of the specimen was 15 mm, thickness was about 1 mm (7 plies for CF/PA6 and 4 plies for CF/PP), longitudinal length was 250 mm, and the distance between tabs was 150 mm.

After the RRT, detailed examination on the gripping conditions without tabs was carried out using CF/PA6 0° specimen. The gripping condition without tabs is summarized in Table 3.

2.3.2 Specimen in the transverse direction (90° test)

Specimens with tabs and without tabs were compared in both materials. The tab materials and specifications were the same as 0° test. The width of the specimen was 25 mm, thickness was about 2 mm (14 plies for CF/PA6 and 8 plies for CF/PP), longitudinal length was 250 mm, and the distance between tabs was 150 mm.

Gripping condition	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
Force control :											
H = Hydraulic	M	H	M	H	H	H	M	M	H	M	M
M = Manual screw			: Precise	: Precise				: Precise		: Precise	
Roughness of grip face :											
L = Large (> 1mm)											
M = Middle (< 1mm)	M	F	F	F	M	F	M	M	M	L	M
F = Fine											
(< 0.25mm or Carbide)											
Abrasive paper ?											
Y = Yes	Y	Y	N	N	Y	N	Y	N	N	N	N
N = No	: double										

Table 3: Gripping conditions of 0° tensile test for CF/PA6 specimen.

2.4 Tensile Test

Tests were carried out at a crosshead speed of 2 mm/min for 0° tests and 1 mm/min for 90° tests. Types of gripping force control were hydraulic or manual screw dependent on laboratories. Tensile strain was measured by extensometer whose gauge length was 50 mm. Elastic modulus was calculated from the chord modulus between 0.05 % and 0.25 % strains for 0° tests and 90° tests. Strength was obtained as the maximum of tensile stress at failure of specimen.

2.5 Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis was carried out to verify the results. Repeatability, which concerns the variability between independent test results, was examined by using the following expression:

$$s_r = \sqrt{\sum s^2 / p} \quad (1)$$

where s_r is the repeatability standard deviation, s is the standard deviation within each laboratory, and p is the number of laboratories. Reproducibility, which deals with the variability in different laboratories, was examined by using the following expression:

$$s_L = \sqrt{\sum (\bar{y} - \bar{\bar{y}})^2 / (p-1)} \quad (1)$$

where s_L is the reproducibility standard deviation, \bar{y} is the average of each laboratory, and $\bar{\bar{y}}$ is the average of all results.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Test in CF/PA6

Figures 1, 2 and Table 4 show the results of CF/PA6 tensile tests in 0° and 90° directions. Figures indicate the average and standard deviation within each laboratory as well as those of all data. In Table 4, CV represents the coefficient of variation, and $(CV)_r$ and $(CV)_L$ correspond to the coefficient of variation within laboratory and that between laboratories, respectively.

Figure 1: Round robin results of CF/PA6 0° tensile strength (left) and modulus (right) – Error bars indicate standard deviation. Total means the mean values and standard deviations of all results.

Figure 2: Round robin results of CF/PA6 90° tensile strength (left) and modulus (right) – Error bars indicate standard deviation. Total means the mean values and standard deviations of all results.

Tensile direction	Tabs	Strength and elastic modulus	Average of all data	CV of all data [%]	$(CV)_r$ [%]	$(CV)_L$ [%]
0°	With tabs	σ	2010 MPa	4.4	4.3	2.1
		E	106 GPa	3.4	2.4	3.0
	Tab-less	σ	1760 MPa	13.6	4.4	14.5
		E	107 GPa	3.0	3.3	0.5
90°	With tabs	σ	37 MPa	18.0	17.6	4.8
		E	6.2 GPa	7.6	3.1	7.7
	Tab-less	σ	38 MPa	10.4	13.4	6.8
		E	6.3 GPa	7.8	5.3	6.1

Table 4: Results of CF/PA6 tensile tests

For 0° strength, CVs by tests with tabs are enough small. However, $(CV)_L$ is larger than $(CV)_r$ in case of tab-less test. This indicates that there were significant differences between laboratories. This is caused by the fact that gripping conditions without tab were rather different between laboratories. These gripping conditions from five laboratories correspond to No. 1, 4, 7, 9 and 11 in Table 3. Gripping condition without tab influences the result of 0° tensile strength significantly.

For 90° strength in both cases of with-tabs and tab-less, CV of all data is almost equal to $(CV)_r$ and larger than $(CV)_L$. This indicates that the variance was not caused by the difference between laboratories but by the difference between specimens. In addition, CVs by tests with tabs are larger than those without tabs. These results suggest that there were some factors to weaken the strength of the specimen through its manufacturing process including tab bonding.

3.2 Test in CF/PP

Figures 3, 4 and Table 5 show the results of CF/PP tensile tests in 0° and 90° directions. Figures indicate the average and standard deviation within each laboratory as well as those of all data. In Table 5, CV represents the coefficient of variation, and $(CV)_r$ and $(CV)_L$ correspond to the coefficient of variation within laboratory and that between laboratories, respectively.

For 0° strength, CV by tests with tabs is larger than CV by tests without tabs, in contradiction to CF/PA6. The variance of 0° strength with tabs was caused by tab-debonding under tensile load, because PP has low adhesive characteristics. It depended on gripping force of tensile machine whether tab-debonding or tab failure occurs.

For 90° test results, the strengths were so low in both cases with and without tab that the calculated elastic moduli were meaningless. This was caused by low interfacial adhesion between carbon fiber and PP. In order to obtain elastic modulus in 90° direction precisely, it is needed to improve adhesive strength of interfaces between CF and PP.

Figure 3: Round robin results of CF/PP 0° tensile strength (left) and modulus (right) – Error bars indicate standard deviation. Total means the mean values and standard deviations of all results.

Figure 4: Round robin results of CF/PP 90° tensile strength (left) and modulus (right) – Error bars indicate standard deviation. Total means the mean values and standard deviations of all results.

Tensile direction	Tabs	Strength and elastic modulus	Average of all data	CV of all data [%]	(CV) _r [%]	(CV) _L [%]
0°	With tabs	σ	445 MPa	33.2	14.7	36.1
		E	52 GPa	5.7	4.3	5.0
	Tab-less	σ	730 MPa	8.0	7.3	4.8
		E	53 GPa	4.6	4.3	3.9
90°	With tabs	σ	6.9 MPa	17.8	15.7	11.5
		E	2.8 GPa	15.6	8.2	15.1
	Tab-less	σ	6.3 MPa	18.7	18.0	10.3
		E	2.8 GPa	10.7	8.7	12.6

Table 5: Results of CF/PP tensile tests

Figure 5: Comparison of CF/PA6 0° tensile strength between gripping conditions.

3.3 Effect of Gripping condition in CF/PA6 0° Test

Figure 5 shows a comparison of CF/PA6 0° tensile strengths between gripping conditions without tab. After the RRT mentioned above, some additional tests were carried out to investigate the other gripping conditions different from the RRT. Numbers in Figure 5 correspond to the numbers for gripping conditions indicated in Table 3, respectively. The leftmost bar indicates the result by test with tabs in the RRT. The dash line indicates a benchmark that equals to the lower limit calculated by subtracting the standard deviation from the average of the value by test with tabs of Laboratory A in Figure 1. Comparing the lower limits by tab-less conditions, No. 1, 2, 3 and 4, with the result by tab-bonding, their gripping conditions, which are adding a few abrasive papers, controlling the gripping force precisely, and adjusting the roughness of grip faces, are acceptable as alternative methods for tab-bonding.

4 CONCLUSIONS

For the cases of both CF/PA6 and CF/PP specimens in the fiber direction, there were significant differences between the strengths with tabs and without tab. Tab-less test in CF/PA6 caused some difference between their strengths due to its gripping condition. Some ideas for gripping method without tab can prevent the specimen's strength from underestimating. On the other hand, tab-debonding occurred in CF/PP test with tabs. In this case, tab-less is preferable. In both thermoplastic composite materials, tab-less is recommended because the preparation of the specimen is easier than tab bonding. We need further researches on the gripping force, abrasive paper, and roughness of grip faces.

For the case of the specimen in transverse direction, there was no significant difference between with tabs and without tab. The variances of strength are not caused by the different gripping condition between laboratories but by the difference between specimens. However, tab-bonding seemed to weaken the transverse strength in CF/PA6. Tab-less is also recommended in transverse tensile test.

Based on these RRT results, a revision for tab condition in tensile test method will be planed at ISO/TC61/SC13/WG2, focusing on thermoplastic composite materials.

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